

TransformAr

Accelerating and upscaling transformational adaptation in
Europe: demonstration of water-related innovation
packages

Dissemination final report

Deliverable D7.6

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PROJECT SUMMARY

Climate change impacts are here and now. The impacts on people, prosperity and planet are already pervasive but unevenly distributed, as stated in the new EU Blueprint strategy (European Commission-EC, 2019). To reduce climate-related risks, the EC and the IPCC agree that transformational adaptation is essential. The TransformAr project aims to develop and demonstrate products and services to launch and accelerate large-scale and disruptive adaptive process for transformational adaptation in vulnerable regions and communities across Europe. The 6 TransformAr lighthouse demonstrators face a common challenge: water-related risks and impacts of climate change. Based on existing successful initiatives, the project will develop, test and demonstrate solutions and pathways, integrated in Innovation Packages, in 6 territories. Transformational pathways, including an integrated risk assessment approach are co-developed by means of 9 Transformational Adaptive Blocks. A set of 22 tested actionable adaptive solutions are tested and demonstrated, ranging from nature-based solutions, innovative technologies, financing, insurance and governance models, awareness and behavioral change solutions. The project team, led by the University of Antwerp, gathers 22 partners from 11 countries and a well-balanced mix of sectoral and adaptation experts (5 RTOs and 1 SME), paired with 6 territories (4 local authorities and 2 charities), 8 additional solutions providers and 1 EU water-related NPO specialized that will support to structure a European Community of practice. Massive resilience increase and acceleration of transformation adaptation will be fostered by clustering various investors, testing bankable solutions, and defining viable (non-)commercial exploitation strategy for the TransformAr solutions, products and services.

More information on the project can be found on www.transformar.eu.

OBJECTIVE AND EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This report is part of the deliverables of the project TransformAr which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 innovation action programme under grant agreement no. 101036683.

The aim of this final dissemination report (D7.6) is to provide an extensive account of the dissemination activities that have been implemented throughout the duration of the project.

This report demonstrates that TransformAr implemented a well-defined dissemination strategy throughout the project, effectively reaching key stakeholders to maximise the uptake of its results. Project partners played a central role in these efforts, actively raising awareness and engaging target audiences with tailored messages, participating in numerous international events, and publishing articles in scientific journals.

TransformAr maintained a strong presence at a wide range of events, including conferences and workshops, ensuring constant visibility and knowledge sharing. The project also actively cultivated collaborations with initiatives and stakeholders related to the climate change adaptation sector, strengthening its network and amplifying its impact.

Dissemination performance was systematically monitored and evaluated, ensuring steady progress toward the project's awareness and engagement objectives.

This deliverable demonstrates that TransformAr fulfils the requirements set out in the Grant Agreement to disseminate results (GA article 29) and to promote the action (GA article 28), and in the Horizon 2020 participation Rules for Participation (Regulation (EU) No 1290/2013, article 43 on exploitation and dissemination of results)¹.

¹ Regulation (EU) No 1290/2013 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 11 December 2013 laying down the rules for participation and dissemination in "Horizon 2020 - the Framework Programme for Research and Innovation (2014-2020)" and repealing Regulation (EC) No 1906/2006.

1. INTRODUCTION

The success of the TransformAr project is highly dependent on well-coordinated dissemination activities. Consequently, TransformAr partners led and participated to specific tasks related to dissemination within WP7 “Structuring a EU transformational adaptation community of practice”. This work package relies strongly on communication and dissemination activities to reach its objective of structuring a community of practice. Therefore, it includes the following dissemination-related activities:

- **T7.2 Building and implementation of a communication strategy**
Task description: This task deals with the definition of the basis for a multi-actor and multi-channel communication and dissemination strategy.
- **T7.3 Building and implementation of dissemination strategy**
Task description: The dissemination strategy of TransformAr, described within the Plan for Dissemination of the project’s Results (D7.2, common plan for dissemination and communication in T7.2, updated in M6) includes:
 - T7.3.1: Field trips “Open Days” to the 6 Demonstrators
 - T7.3.2: Organisation of the final conference
 - T7.3.3: Other regular dissemination activities

The activities described in this deliverable were planned in the Communication and Dissemination Plan (D7.2) submitted at Month 6 and regularly updated throughout the project – specifically at Months 18 and 36.

As outlined in D7.2, TransformAr’s dissemination activities aim to enable a rapid and far-reaching change through the development of Innovation Packages and ensure a long-term use of the project’s results. It was also highlighted that some of the main dissemination goals should be reflected within the project’s daily activities, especially when it comes to contributing to EU-wide knowledge exchange between climate adaptation practitioners, and connecting and informing the scientific institutions, policymakers and general public.

This report provides a comprehensive assessment of the dissemination activities implemented throughout the TransformAr project from its launch in October 2021. These activities are presented by channels (e.g., scientific publications, conferences), and within each section the description will be organised around the following points: a brief reminder of the activity’s main purpose, a description of the activity as such, and an assessment of its overall impact. Finally, a conclusion will summarize the results and lessons learned.

2. LIST OF PARTNERS

TransformAr partners are the following:

No	Participant organisation English name	Acronym	Country
1	University of Antwerp	UA	Belgium
2	Euro-Mediterranean Center on Climate Change	CMCC	Italy
3	ACTIERRA	ACTIERRA	France
4	E3-Modelling	E3M	Greece
5	Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research	PIK	Germany
6	Verhaert New Products and Services nv	VERHAERT	Belgium

7	Fundación Empresa – Universidad Gallega	FEUGA	Spain
8	National Centre for Scientific Research “Demokritos”	NCSR	Greece
9	Czech University of Life Sciences Prague	CZU	Czech Republic
10	LUT University	LUT	Finland
11	Norwegian University of Science and Technology	NTNU	Norway
12	University of Vigo	UVIGO	Spain
13	Epsilon Malta Ltd	EPSILON	Malta
14	French Ecological Transition National Agency	ADEME	France
15	Westcountry Rivers Trust	WRT	United Kingdom
16	Mediterranean Sea and Coast	MEDSEA	Italy
17	CETMAR	CETMAR	Spain
18	City of Lappeenranta	LAPP	Finland
19	Municipality of Egaleo	MOE	Greece
20	Water Europe	WE	Belgium
21	Euroquality	EQY	France
22	Gjøvik municipality	MOG	Norway

3. DISSEMINATION MATERIALS

During the first months of the TransformAr project, Water Europe has developed the graphical charter and made available to the consortium as well as to the general public the following supports used for both communication and dissemination activities of the project.

These materials are key elements of the TransformAr communication and dissemination strategy and, as such, were mobilised in various situations, both in-person and online.

Below are some examples of such dissemination materials that were used during the four years of TransformAr, with (i) global dissemination material created by Water Europe and available on the TransformAr website (direct link [here](#)) and available to partners on the project’s SharePoint – see Figures 1 and 2; and tailored supporting materials for local dissemination purposes, designed by local partners from Demonstrator regions and cities – see Figures 3 and 4.

TransformAr
Accelerating and upscaling transformational adaptation in Europe:
DEMONSTRATION OF WATER-RELATED INNOVATION PACKAGES

Challenges
Climate change is happening today, so we have to build a more resilient tomorrow. The latest in the new EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change (2022). The IPCC report on impacts, adaptation and vulnerability (2022) shows that although progress in adaptation across all sectors and regions has been observed, many initiatives prioritize immediate and near-term climate risk reduction which reduces the opportunity for transformational adaptation.

What will TransformAr do?
The project will develop an adaptive process based on open innovation, user-friendly and accessible climate data services, actionable solutions and large-scale experimentation. This will be supported by the implementation of innovation packages built to increase communities' social and climate resilience.

6 demonstrators

- City of Lappeenranta, Finland**
 - Main focus:
 - Urban runoff system to deal with stormwater
 - Ecosystems and nature-based solutions
- Guadeloupe Archipelago, France**
 - Main focus:
 - Sustainable Tourism
 - New financing models
 - Agricultural models for a more diverse and resilient crops
- Gjovik municipality, Norway**
 - Gjovik municipality is a follower and replicator for Lappeenranta demonstration because of the similarities in climate vulnerability regarding urban planning and water management.
- Galicia region, Spain**
 - Main focus:
 - Climate change impact on the coastal aquaculture
 - Climate culture and shell fishing on foot impacted by coastal oceanographic and hydrological changes
- West Country region, UK**
 - Main focus:
 - Maintainable water business sector
 - Impacted river habitat and species
 - Agriculture and nutrient savings
- Oristano, Italy**
 - Main focus:
 - Nutrients load reduction and flood management
 - Nature conservation for cultural and natural heritage
- City of Egaleo, Greece**
 - Main focus:
 - Socially vulnerable groups exposure to pollution-related climate change
 - Innovative solutions and urban planning for outdoor and indoor activities that are not climate-proof

Objectives and impact

- Communicate the Transformational Adaptive Blocks necessary regions or community in Europe wanting to tackle transformational adaptation (TA);
- Deliver user-friendly, accessible and comprehensive multi-sector cross-scale services relevant to transformational adaptation to water-related challenges and fit the needs of public and private;
- Test the potential of specific innovations to enable rapid and far-reaching change in the behaviour of demonstrators
- Accelerate investment in Transformational Adaptation across the EU by means of demonstrating bankability and meeting financial objectives
- Consolidate a catalogue of solutions and Phases and guidance documents, and an understanding of the applicability and performance of forms of solutions for transformational adaptation.

Expected results

- Support the European Green Deal targets, in particular the new EU Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change, the EU Mission Climate Adaptation, the EU Biodiversity Strategy and circular economy strategies, the objectives of the European Union's Horizon 2020, as well as the Clean Air Programme for Europe
- Contribute to the economic restart from the Covid-19 recession and foster from biodiversity change, coastal regions and sectors of society to increase climate resilience.
- Contribute to social acceptance and social resilience
- Increase the community resilience and capacity to cope with unavoidable effects of climate change.

About TransformAr

- Start date: 01 October 2021
- Duration: 48 months
- Budget: € 12 703 322.30
- Aim: TransformAr will develop into solutions and pathways essential for climate and social resilience to achieve rapid and far-reaching transformational adaptation (TA).
- Project coordination: Prof. Jan Coudis, University of Antwerp

A consortium of 22 partners and 12 countries

Contact us:

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement 101035685

Figure 1. TransformAr overview poster.

Figure 2. TransformAr brochure at Water Knowledge Europe 2023.

Figure 3. Local brochure for local dissemination in Guadeloupe Archipelago, France.

Figure 4. Two roll-up banners used for local dissemination at Egaleo, Greece.

4. REPORT ON DISSEMINATION ACTIVITIES

4.1. Introduction

Dissemination stands for the public disclosure of the project's results and implies an active process of promotion and awareness-raising around the latter from the beginning of the project to its end. The goal is to make the project results stemming from research known to different stakeholder groups, each targeted in a specific way. As outlined in D7.2, these target groups correspond to seven (7) different categories, namely:

1. **Change-agents:** organisations or individuals having the ability to tackle barriers to adaptation and/or mobilise relevant stakeholders;
2. **Key Community Systems stakeholders;**
3. **Citizens and citizen organisations;**
4. **Private sector;**
5. **Investors;**
6. **Scientific community;**
7. **Policymakers** at regional, national and EU levels.

The key messages addressed to each of these target groups are outlined in D7.2, section 1.5.

4.2. Scientific publications

4.2.1. Purpose of the activity

The publication of scientific articles by the TransformAr project partners aims at sharing the project's results with the scientific community. The main idea behind scientific publications is to increase the project's impact, hence contributing to the advancement of research on transformational adaptation.

4.2.2. Description of the activity

In total, TransformAr partners have published 8 scientific publications between October 2021 and July 2025. 13 scientific publications are still in the pipeline for the remaining months of the project. A detailed table on the project's scientific publications, linked to the project's relevant Work Packages, can be found in Annex 1.

4.3. Summary sheets

4.3.1. Purpose of the activity

The redaction of summary sheets was implemented to make technical deliverables more accessible to the general public. By providing a shorter and simplified format, the idea was for the TransformAr project partners to be able to disseminate the results to a wider audience and therefore increase the project's impact.

4.3.2. Description of the activity

So far, summary sheets for seven deliverables were finalised and uploaded on the website:

- **D1.2** Stakeholder matrix and innovation (<https://transformar.eu/storage/2025/06/D1.2-Summary-sheet.pdf>)
- **D2.2** Modelling customization and implementation report (<https://transformar.eu/storage/2025/06/D2.2-Summary-sheet.pdf>)

- **D3.1** Governance framework tool and report (<https://transformar.eu/storage/2025/06/D3.1-Summary-sheet-1.pdf>)
- **D3.4** Tools on the avoided damages and benefits per demonstrator (<https://transformar.eu/storage/2025/06/D3.4-D3.5-Summary-sheet.pdf>)
- **D3.6** Replicable socio-economic impact assessment tools of transformational pathways (<https://transformar.eu/storage/2025/06/D3.6-Summary-sheet-1.pdf>)
- **D3.7** Toolkit for adaptive action planning (<https://transformar.eu/storage/2025/06/D3.7-summary-sheet-TransformAr-revised.pdf>)
- **D6.1** Results on the public acceptance and preferences (https://transformar.eu/storage/2025/06/D6.1-Summary-sheet_final-1.pdf)

To ensure the summary sheet's diffusion to the general public, a communication campaign is ongoing on social media (LinkedIn), including links to the summary sheets, the full deliverables, and the "Results" page on the website.

More summary sheets on technical deliverables are planned and will be added to the website when they are finalised. The upcoming summary sheets include the main deliverables of WP2 (D2.3, D2.4, D2.5, D2.6), WP4 (D4.6), WP5 (D5.3, D5.4, D5.5, D5.7, D5.9) and WP6 (D6.2, D6.4, D6.5).

4.4. Green Deal Success Stories and Mission Adaptation Stories

4.4.1. Purpose of the activity

Green Deal Success Stories and Mission Adaptation Stories aim to share the key innovative outputs reflected through the experience of demonstrators. One of the main objectives is to communicate the lessons learned and the good practices regarding the process of implementing climate adaptation solutions, to inspire others to take action on climate adaptation.

4.4.2. Description of the activity

All 6 demonstrators as well as the one replicator have submitted Mission Adaptation stories, focusing on one implemented solution. Currently 4 stories are accessible online:

- The Galician demonstrator focused on the [Resilience Index](#), a key solution that contributed to climate adaptation in the mussel aquaculture sector.
- The Sardinian demonstrator showcases its [coastal contract](#), a multi-level approach to wetland governance.
- The Guadeloupien demonstrator highlighted the [Local Adaptation Fund](#), a tool that unites local public and private investor to support innovative agricultural projects.
- The Finish demonstrator and Norwegian replicator focused on the [stormwater management and the results of a willingness to pay study](#) conducted in both countries.

The UK and Greek demonstrators submitted stories on respectively the NBS implementation and Awareness-raising modules for young people, that are currently under review and will soon be published.

In addition to the Mission Adaptation stories, 2 Green Deal Success Stories have been published, focusing on the Norwegian replicator's citizen app solution ([Empowering communities for climate resilience: Gjøvik's flood detection innovation](#)) and on the coastal contract implemented in Sardinian ([Innovative governance tool to manage and protect wetlands](#)).

4.5. Videos

4.5.1. Purpose of the activity

Videos were produced throughout the project to showcase its key outcomes—presenting the overall concept, implemented solutions. Each demonstration site was featured in a dedicated video, illustrating TransformAr’s contributions in those regions. The videos primarily targeted the general public, aiming to communicate results in an accessible and engaging way.

4.5.2. Description of the activity

12 videos were produced and published on the TransformAr YouTube channel (<https://www.youtube.com/@transformar8347>):

Horizon Results Booster: Stakeholder engagement for climate adaptation
(<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=pMwUIMMF1mg>)

In collaboration with REGILIENCE, ARSINOE and Impetus, supported by Horizon Results Booster Module B, the video presents the different strategies for fostering collaboration and building resilience.

6 Open days videos from Demonstrators

In the second year of the project, all demonstrators organised open events at local level to bring stakeholders together to dive deeper into the implemented solution in each demonstrator.

Those moments were captured, and the highlights were compiled in 6 different videos and published on YouTube.

[TransformAr Oristano Open Day: Climate Adaptation & Solutions for the Future](#)

[TransformAr Project Open Day Highlights | Lappeenranta Greenreality Carnival 2024](#)

[Innovating Catchment Management Solutions TransformAr Open Days in the Westcountry Region](#)

[TransformAr Open Day: Climate Adaptation Solutions for Galicia's Mussel and Clam Sectors](#)

[TransformAr Open Day – City of Egaleo: Showcasing Climate Resilience Solutions](#)

[TransformAr Open Day – Guadalupe: Climate Change Adaptation in Agriculture & Tourism](#)

Figure 5. 6 snapshots of each Open day videos

5 solution-focused videos

4 different videos were also produced to showcase the different solutions implemented during the project at different demonstration sites. 1 video is focused on the digital and technological solutions implementation on the Galicia, Egaleo and Lappeenranta demonstrators.

Currently, only 1 teaser ([Bringing innovative digital and technological solutions to help cities - TransformAr project](#)) is available on the YouTube channel of the project.

The other 3 are all focusing on the implementation of Nature-based solutions in the Westcountry region, Lappeenranta and Oristino demonstrators.

In addition, the Local Adaptation Fund implemented in Guadeloupe was explained in a detailed video showcasing the 6 projects funded under that solution ([Innovative Climate Adaptation in Guadeloupe: TransformAr's Local Adaptation Fund](#)).

4.6. Participation in conferences and events

4.6.1. Purpose of the activity

Participating in conferences and events is an essential aspect of the project's dissemination as it allows the TransformAr consortium to reach some of the targeted audiences, such as researchers, policymakers, change agents and investors. These occasions are opportunities to have in-person meetings and discussions with the target groups, enabling TransformAr partners to share information about the project with more impact.

4.6.2. Description of the activity

European and international events

Date	Event	Collaboration with other projects
April 2022	WE participated to the Pan-European Regional Preparatory Meeting for the UN 2023 Water Conference where specific reference was made to TransformAr project.	No
May 2022	UA and EQY participated to the First Mission Adaptation Forum in Brussels, to network with other regions that signed the Mission Charter.	No
June 2022	CMCC also participated to EU level events: the 6th European Agroforestry event and the XXIV National Agrometeorology Conference, with a session on "A modelling platform to assess the impact of climate change on crop water requirements at local and regional scale".	No
September 2022	ADEME participated to a session on Showcasing coastal cities adaptation efforts and resilient ways for the transition during the EU Regions Week: "Assessing climate services for	No

	ecosystem-based adaptation in European Coastal Cities and Towns”.	
April 2023	CETMAR presented the Playbook from WP3 and its application to the Galician aquaculture sector at the second REGILIENCE Open Training Session (online).	Yes: REGILIENCE
June 2023	UA, ACTIERRA, CZU and FEUGA participated in the ECCA 2023 in Dublin, Ireland. This was for a joint session with REGILIENCE (co-organiser), ARSINOE and IMPETUS.	Yes: REGILIENCE, ARSINOE, IMPETUS
December 2023	WE attended the COP 28 in Dubai and shared information about TransformAr at the Water Pavilion.	No
March 2024	UA participated in the Open Training Session (online) organised by REGILIENCE, and showcased the governance solutions (Resilience Index, Coastal Contract, Bankability of NBS, Local Adaptation Fund) of the project.	Yes: REILIENCE
June 2024	ACTIERRA and CZU also participated in the EURESFO 2024 in Valencia, Spain. The event was co-organised by REGILIENCE, and ACTIERRA presented work done in the Guadeloupe demonstrator on the Local Adaptation Fund.	Yes: REGILIENCE
July 2024	CETMAR presented the digital and technological solutions implemented in the Galician demonstrator during the IX International Symposium on Marine Sciences (ISMS 2024).	No
	Th UA coordination team presented TransformAr activities to the “Meet and share” event for EU Missions National Contact Points (NCPs) with sister projects and other initiatives.	Yes: ARSINOE, IMPETUS, REGILIENCE, Pathways2Resilience, CLIMAAX
September 2024	LAPP presented lessons learned from its storm water management solution to a Mission Adaptation online event on Flood Resilience: Strategies and Solutions for a Safer Future is organised by the Mission Implementation Platform for Adaptation to Climate Change (MIP4Adapt).	Yes: MIP4Adapt
February 2025	PIK shared how heat exposure across Europe impact health, outdoor work conditions, showcasing the PIK platform . The webinar has been organised by REGILIENCE.	Yes: REGILIENCE
March 2025	ACTIERRA participated in a parallel session together with ICLEI, Pathway2Resilience, Regions4Climate, REGILIENCE and CARDIMED, during the Climate Change Europe-Africa 2025 Summit in Marseille, to present on transformative action for a resilient Europe.	Yes: Pathway2Resilience, Regions4Climate, REGILIENCE, CARDIMED
	The Municipality of Egaleo presented their work on engaging students and the wider community in climate action in Greece during the European Climate Pact Annual Event.	No

April 2025	NTNU participated in the PCP WISE webinar and presented the digital and technological solutions implemented within the project.	Yes: PCP WISE
May 2025	CZU presented the outputs of the TransformAr project at EIT Food Forum (Accelerating and Rescaling Climate Change Transformative Adaptation Measures in Europe).	No
June 2025	UA and WRT presented in a joint session with CLIMATEFIT the key results from qualitative research on the bankability of climate adaptation projects at ECCA 2025. CZU demonstrated the innovative tools (one of the TransformAr pilot facility, the Lappeenranta's pioneering urban biofiltration system) which were developed in project Transformar to support #LocalClimateAction at ECCA 2025.	Yes: CLIMATEFIT
	ADEME presented the Local Adaptation Fund in the Outermost regions driving climate resilience in the EU session, moderated by REGIANCE. The city of Lappeenranta together with CZU Prague presented how to adapt to stormwater risks through nature-based solutions, during the EURESFO warm-up workshop.	Yes: REGIANCE
	UA presented results from the Discrete Choice Experiment conducted for Finland and Norway for stormwater management at the 30 th Annual Conference of the European Association of Environmental and Resource Economists.	No
July 2025	UA presented the replicability assessment tool during the Open training session (online) organised by REGIANCE.	Yes: REGIANCE
July 2025	CZU presented the adaptive approach within the TransformAr project at IEES 2025. Exchange of experience regarding large-scale implementation of nature-based measures (NBS) and mapping of approaches to impact modeling and decision-making tools for municipalities.	No

Table 1. TransformAr at European and international events

National and local events

Date	Event	Country
December 2021	MOG presented the TransformAr project and participated in a panel debate on climate change adaptation in a hybrid seminar on the EU missions in Oslo.	Oslo, Norway
March 2022	UA and ACTERRA participated to an event organised for the French Presidency of the Council of the EU in Paris, for which they presented the stakeholders and citizens engagement within TransformAr.	Paris, France

July & August 2022	WRT participated to local dissemination events to disseminate the project to key local actors and change agents.	Devon, UK
September 2022	MEDSEA attended the Bleu Waves event, on Circular Economy for the Sea in Sardinia to disseminate work done on the Sardinia case study within TransformAr to the local citizens and scientific community.	Sardinia, Italy
	UVIGO joined the national Coastal Geomorphology Conference to discuss about their work on the Galician demonstrator within TransformAr.	Galicia, Spain
September 2023	MOG and NTNU participated to a local science event (“Pint of Science” format) to present TransformAr to local citizens.	Lappeenranta, Finland
May 2024	LUT participated in a local Water Workshop online pitching event to reflect on Lappeenranta’s activities.	Lappeenranta, Finland
June 2024	The Municipality of Egaleo, took part in the Attica green Expo and showcased their local initiatives through a booth.	Greece
March 2025	The Municipality of Gjovik gave insights about the willingness to pay for stormwater management, presented the the playbook for transformational adaptation and citizen app, during an event on Climate adaptation of the wastewater system.	Gjovik, Norway
June 2025	<p>CZU participated in co-creating the emerging CEE Climate Platform - a new initiative dedicated to strengthening climate action in Central and Eastern Europe.</p> <p>At the Expert Group meeting of the CEE Climate Week CZU connected the local action with European policy frameworks. The key contributions of TransformAr and CZU to the CEE Climate Platform initiative are the implementation of Innovation Packages in six demonstrator regions. Transfer of transformational adaptation methodologies to the CEE context and Facilitation of stakeholder engagement and co-creation processes.</p> <p>Participants: Representatives of the European Commission, the Ministry of the Environment of the Czech Republic, UNFCCC, cities, academic institutions and platforms.</p>	Prague, CZ

Table 2. TransformAr at local events

4.7. Organisation of workshops, webinars and/or seminars

4.7.1. Purpose of the activity

Workshops, webinars and Open Days were organised to share TransformAr’s scientific breakthrough on transformational adaptation and to showcase the project’s activities carried out and solutions implemented in the demonstration sites.

4.7.2. Description of the activity

Local Open Days – flagship events in Demonstrators

6 Open Days were organised by Demonstrators (one Open Day per Demonstrator), with the support of EQY between June 2024 and September 2024. These were key local dissemination events to showcase local adaptation solutions that were co-developed and implemented.

The first 3 Open Days were EU Green week partner events, on the overall theme of Water Resilience. MOE, MEDSEA and LAPP applied and succeeded in being EU Green Week partner events for their Open Days in March 2024. [MOE's Open Day was on 04/06/2024](#), co-organised with their local technical support partner NCSR D at the Climate Innovation Hub. [MEDSEA's Open Day was on 05/07/2024](#) at the Museum of Marceddì, organised with the support of CMCC, and the [LAPP Open Day was held on 29/08/2024](#), during the local GreenReality Carnival and in collaboration with LUT.

The remaining 3 Open Days were all held in September 2024, with [WRT's Open Day on 13/09/2024](#), [ADEME's on 16/09/2024](#) – co-organised with ACTIERRA and VERHAERT and [CETMAR's event on 18/09/2024](#), co-organised with FEUGA and UVIGO.

Figure 6. Picture from the Egaleo Open Day held in June 2024.

Following those events, the main outcomes and insights were shared on the project's website.

Final consultation workshop at local level

5 consultation workshops were organised by the demonstrator to showcase the results that came out of the first round of consultation workshops.

May 2024 - CETMAR: The workshop provided updates on climate risks, presented scientific data, and shared progress on the resilience index developed by the University of Vigo's REDE group, with support from CETMAR and IIM-CSIC.

March 2025 – WRT: The workshop provided insights on local climate risks and the implementation of nature-based solutions at the demonstration site. Dedicated time allowed to discuss innovative financing models in resilience.

March 2025 – MEDSEA: The results of the bankability reports were presented focusing on the opportunity of protecting land via NBS. Preliminary results of the monitoring were also shared.

May 2025 – ADEME: The workshop focused on presenting FLAG-funded projects, conducting a SWOT analysis, and working on strategic recommendations for the future of the FLAG.

The consultation workshop in Lappeenranta will happen in August.

Webinars organised by CMCC for the Climate Change Adaptation network

3 thematic webinars were organised by CMCC within their Climate Change Adaptation network activities (see D7.7). The online event address key topics, and allowed to showcase the TransformAr solutions:

- [Climate governance: a springboard for transformational adaptation through informed decision-making - December 2023](#)

This webinar was organised in collaboration with the Mission Implementation Platform (MIP4Adapt) and presented the governance solutions for climate adaptation, implemented in the Galician and Sardinian demonstrator, highlighting data-driven decision making (DDDM) for effective water management.

In total, 276 people attended the webinar.

- [Nature-based solutions \(Nbs\) for climate adaptation – July 2024](#)

This webinar was organised in collaboration with the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change and the Green Deal Support Office. It explored Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) for climate adaptation, specifically focusing on how to identify the root causes of the problem, including different typologies and implementation on the ground, their financing mechanisms and possible replication and upscale.

In total, 262 people attended the webinar.

- [Climate finance for climate adaptation and nature restoration – October 2024](#)

This webinar was organised in collaboration with the Green Deal Support Office Working Group on Biodiversity and Climate Change. Innovative tools and mechanisms to unlock financing and private investment for climate adaptation and nature restoration were presented. It focused on key elements to bridge the adaptation finance gap, including bankability criteria for adaptation projects, the design of local investment strategies, and the role of the insurance sector.

In total, 107 people attended the webinar.

Organisation of the final consortium meeting with a public session

To showcase the main results of TransformAr, and allow the exchange of good practices in adaptation solutions at regional or city scale, a public session will be held on September 11 in Brussels.

12:30 - 13:00	Welcome and registration
13:00 – 13:15	<p>Advancing Climate Resilience in Europe</p> <p><i>Amalie Bjornavold</i>, Policy Officer DG Agriculture and Rural Development, European Commission</p>
13:15 – 13:30	<p>TransformAr’s approach and achievements</p> <p><i>Jan Cools</i>, TransformAr coordinator, University of Antwerp</p>
13:30 – 14:15	<p>Transformational adaptation in action: regional feedback, replication potential, and remaining gaps</p> <p>Moderator: TBC – REGILIENCE project</p> <p>Speakers:</p>

	<p><i>Manuel Tasende</i>, Head of the Aquaculture Technological Innovation Service, TransformAr Galician demonstrator</p> <p><i>Milo Pinna</i>, Municipality of Terralba, TransformAr sardinian demonstrator</p> <p><i>TBC</i>, Municipality of Gjovik, TransformAr Norwegian replicator</p>
14:15 – 14:30	<p>From challenge to change: addressing water-related climate risks through regional innovation</p> <p>Presenters: TBC</p>
14:30 – 15:00	<p>Coffee break & networking</p>
15:30 – 17:00	<p>TransformAr in practice: Interactive stations showcasing the main actionable results and demonstration solutions</p> <p>Discover and discuss the different topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Financing of climate change adaptation - TransformAr explored ways to engage private investors by consulting stakeholders at European and local levels. In TransformAr, we also experimented with the Local Adaptation Fund in Guadeloupe and Nutrient Credit Schemes (following a Payment for Ecosystem Services approach) in the West Country Region in England. • Nature-based solutions: design and monitoring – While nature-based solutions are widely considered cost-effective for climate change adaptation in urban and agricultural settings, their practical design and impact measurement remain challenging. TransformAr offers examples from Lappeenranta (Finland) and the West Country (England) to address these issues. • Scorecards for Resilience & Transformational Adaptation: To respond to the EU adaptation mission's request for rapid and transformative climate resilience, it is essential to effectively monitor progress. TransformAr has presented tools such as scorecard for Transformational Adaptation and the Resilience Index for Aquaculture in Galicia, Spain. • Coastal adaptation: European coastal regions face high climate risks. TransformAr showcases two coastal demonstrators: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Bay of Oristano, Sardinia – focused on innovative governance through a coastal contract and smart gates to control flow and water quality ○ Galicia, Spain – developed adaptation solutions for the aquaculture, especially the clam and mussel sector. • Adaptation pathways: The pathways approach offers a flexible, action-oriented method for climate adaptation planning at regional and city levels. While increasingly used in EU projects, it remains experimental, with varied methodologies and data challenges. This discussion shares key lessons from a comparative analysis of its application.
17:00 – 17:30	<p>Wrap up and remaining gaps</p> <p><i>Jan Cools</i>, TransformAr coordinator, University of Antwerp</p>

17:30	End of the event
-------	------------------

Table 3. Tentative agenda of the public afternoon

4.8. Links to existing initiatives and sister projects

4.8.1. Purpose of the activity

TransformAr has established links especially with sister projects with the main objective of following and sharing each project's accomplishment, exchanging best practices, but also creating communication materials together to increase their reach.

4.8.2. Description of the activity

Joint dissemination activities

TransformAr co-organised and actively participated in various dissemination activities with sister projects. In June 2022, a first meeting between the four projects kicked off the collaboration, during which possible synergies in stakeholder engagement and monitoring were discussed.

With ARSINOE

TransformAr, together with other sister projects led by [ARSINOE](#) co-organised several online seminars:

- **ARSINOE 3rd online seminar - Climate change and its impact on water and public health**
The seminar offered new perspectives and opportunities provided by the water and public health nexus to help address water management and climate change challenges from a systemic vision.
- **ARSINOE 4th online seminar - How can NBS support climate-change adaptation and mitigation in the water sector?**
The seminar built a discussion arena about the perspectives and the opportunities provided by nature-based solutions to help address water management and climate change challenges.
- **ARSINOE 5th Online Seminar -Water-Smart Cities: Navigating Climate-Resilient Sustainable Urbanisation in the Digital Age**
The seminar focused on urbanisation and climate challenges, focusing on water management, leveraging smart tech, data, and governance.
- **ARSINOE 6th Online Seminar - Exploring the effects of climate change on biodiversity**
The seminar focused on the effects of climate change on biodiversity and explored practical solutions.
- **ARSINOE 7th Online Seminar - The Future of Water: A Water Sector Approach for building resilience in a changing climate**
The seminar explored sustainable solutions across policy, technology, and community engagement to build resilience amid climatic uncertainties.

With REGILIENCE

TransformAr project partners participated in 2 open training sessions organised by the REGILIENCE project. Additionally, CETMAR provided a training session at the REGILIENCE Autumn school in October 2023 on "Climate Risk Management – Strategies and Tools for Regional and Local Challenges" presenting the adaptation of the "TransformAr Playbook" for co-designing a roadmap for climate change adaptation in the mussel aquaculture and clam harvesting sectors in Galicia.

The TransformAr coordinator also wrote an opinion article on “Why is EU water policy essential, but insufficient, to achieve climate resilience?” that was published online on the REGILIENCE website in July 2024.

Through the Horizon Results Booster module with REGILIENCE, ARSINOE, IMPETUS

Together with REGILIENCE, ARSINOE, IMPETUS, TransformAr participated in the preparation of inputs for the creation of a factsheet, video and policy brief (see section 4.10) under the Horizon Results Booster module, focused on Stakeholder engagement. All three outputs were delivered in September 2024.

4.9. Other Mission Adaptation and Green Deal Support Office collaboration activities

4.9.1. Purpose of the activity

TransformAr participated in different activities led by the Mission Adaptation and the Green Deal Support Office, which allowed knowledge sharing, fostered collaboration with other EU-funded projects and strengthened the project’s impact.

4.9.2. Description of the activity

TransformAr participated in the Mission Forum launch in January 2023, which also kicked off the Community of Practice on adaptation together with the sister projects.

After this, FEUGA, UA and CMCC participated in three Thematic Working Groups of the Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change:

- *Citizen and Stakeholders engagement Thematic Working Group*: FEUGA contributed to the discussions with two potential axes on the consultation workshops methodology and on an Interactive Innovation Index tool (both from work conducted in WP1);
- *Transformational adaptation Thematic Working Group*: UA contributed to a [Joint Policy Brief](#) on the topic which will be published early 2025, linking to D6.4.
- *Monitoring and evaluation*: UA and CMCC contributed to a [report](#) synthesising key challenges and lessons from monitoring adaptation activities.

Additionally, the Finnish demonstrator contributed to a Best Practice event organised by the Green Deal Support Office, presenting the urban water storm management solution.

4.10. Policy briefs

4.10.1. Purpose of the activity

Policy briefs were designed to showcase knowledge and scientific progress on climate adaptation, particularly by sharing lessons learned and project results. Producing a joint policy brief with sister projects helped foster a shared vision and strengthen the impact of our results.

4.10.2. Description of the activity

Understanding Transformational Adaptation: A shared vision across EU Horizon projects (2025)

This policy brief presents a shared vision on Transformational Adaptation, developed by the Transformational Adaptation Thematic Working Group under the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change's Implementation Platform (MIP4Adapt). It brings together insights from several EU Horizon projects—including TransformAr, Pathways2Resilience, IMPETUS, REGILIENCE, DesirMED, CARDIMED, TRANSCEND, and CLIMATEFIT—to explore the need for systemic, long-term approaches to climate adaptation. The brief defines transformational adaptation, outlines key barriers, and provides practical recommendations to guide decision-makers. The target audience includes EU, regional and local authorities, and practitioners involved in climate adaptation, particularly those working within the framework of the EU Adaptation Mission.

Insights on monitoring climate adaptation activities: Deriving lessons learned from monitoring adaptation activities in projects under the EU Mission on Adaptation

This document presents the work on the mechanisms for monitoring climate resilience and adaptation in three EU Horizon 2020 projects (ARSINOE, IMPETUS, and TransformAr), and a newcomer Horizon Europe project (NATALIE) under the EU Mission on Adaptation to Climate Change. It synthesises the projects' challenges and lessons learned to support future initiatives in their monitoring endeavours, for other mission projects to learn from. The identified challenges include tailoring global frameworks to local needs, identifying data availability, and enhancing interdisciplinary collaboration and stakeholder engagement.

Stakeholder engagement in climate adaptation & resilience (2025)

This Policy Brief Compilation booklet has been produced with the support of Trust-IT Services, provider of the Horizon Results Booster, funded by the European Commission. The Policy Briefs have been written by projects (REGILIENCE, TransformAr, IMPETUS, ARSINOE) and project groups that took part in the Horizon Results Booster. It regroups different approaches for engaging communities and their critical role in shaping climate-resilient development pathways.

5. What comes next

In the last month of the project (July – September 2025) other dissemination activities will take place and finalised by the whole consortium.

Scientific publications

Several publications will be submitted (see Annex 1) and written based on the recently submitted deliverables. Currently, 8 publications have been accepted and will soon be published, and another 5 will be submitted soon. UA is planning to write a paper on D6.5 Innovation packages and E3M on 2.4 Full-scale socio-economic impacts of CC and TA in EU, national and sub-national levels.

Key Exploitable Results

During the last year of the project, the consortium defined the key exploitable results based on discussion and the exploitation activities led by FEUGA:

- TransformAr Playbook
- Data visualisation platform

- Mission adaptation stories
- Green Deal Success Stories
- Three Policy Briefs
- A Replication guide
- A Replicability assessment tool
- An online Scorecard for Transformational Adaptation
- Two Best practices on Stakeholder management and on Change management - regions and local authorities
- Sustainability profiles of solutions
- Specific technological and knowledge adaptation solutions

All results will be made available by the end of the project on different platforms: Project website, Green Deal Projects Support office webpage, MIP4ADAPT, Horizon Results Platform, Climate Innovation Window and Zenodo.

More details will be included in D6.9 Open-access content for CSA-Platform.

Local dissemination

As part of the exploitation and dissemination activities, all demonstrators reflected on the TransformAr results they would like to share with their stakeholders during the last months and beyond the end of the project. This takes the form of a local communication and dissemination strategy.

The Municipality of Egaleo plans to disseminate the Awareness Raising modules, Smart Climate Stations (SCS), the Citizen App Engagement (CAE), Climate Innovation Hub (CIH) and the Demand Analysis for Social Services (DSI). Those results will be shared through: local community workshops, presentations at municipal council and school board meetings, public events under other EU projects and digital dissemination via the municipality's website and social media. The aim of this is to foster replication of solutions in other departments or cities and to embed climate resilience thinking across local governance, education, and civil society.

ADEME is part of another EU-funded project, and will keep working on the FLAG, with a new call for projects launching next year. Additionally, a consortium meeting in Guadeloupe is planned for this project, where the main results of TransformAr will be shared.

The Galician demonstrator will share updates on the implemented solutions with the Marine and Maritime Working Group of red CUROSOE. Additionally, stakeholder engagement guidelines and best practice reports will be shared with local NGOs through workshops. In general, the main outputs of TransformAr will be shared internally by CETMAR.

The full strategy of **WRT** can be found in Annex 2.

The other demonstrators will write a strategy and implement it in the last month.

6. IMPACT

Throughout the project, a wide range of dissemination activities significantly amplified the reach and visibility of TransformAr's results.

By organising targeted workshops and open days, the project actively engaged around 1,000 key stakeholders, including representatives of key community systems (KCS), citizens, change agents, the scientific community, and policymakers.

Beyond these direct engagements, TransformAr extended its impact to around 25,000 stakeholders through its participation in various external events. These included poster and oral presentations as well as video display, reaching 62% citizens, 30% scientific community and a smaller proportion of change agents, KCS stakeholders and policy makers.

TransformAr also established valuable collaborations with other initiatives and projects. TransformAr participated in 3 working groups of the MIP4ADAPT. Through close collaboration with the sister projects, TransformAr showcase its main results in 17 joint events: joint presentations at conferences, participation in webinars and training sessions organised by sister projects. This led to 3 policy briefs being published, an Interactive Innovation Index tool, a report synthesising key challenges and lessons from monitoring adaptation activities. Through the Horizon Results Booster module, TransformAr in collaboration with REGILINCE, ARSIONE, IMPETUS, created a factsheet and video around stakeholder engagement.

While the number of scientific articles published continues to grow, TransformAr has already produced 8 scientific articles, with 13 more expected to be prepared, finalised and published by 2025.

7. CONCLUSION

The TransformAr project ended successfully with considerable effort and involvement of all the partners in the implementation of the dissemination strategy in regards to project activities and results. The consortium was very active in spreading information and sharing content on the TransformAr project.

A strong interest was manifested in the project by the various target groups, including the research community, policymakers, change-agents, and the general public. The extensive dissemination efforts have contributed to the project's overall goal of advancing transformational adaptation and reducing climate-related risks.

In conclusion, the TransformAr project's dissemination activities have played a crucial role in the project results' visibility, promoting its solutions, and engaging key stakeholders in the field of climate adaptation.

The TransformAr website will be maintained beyond the project's official conclusion, hence ensuring continued online accessibility to project results and information until 2030. This strategic decision will allow ongoing dissemination of the project's key findings and support the long-term impact of TransformAr.

ANNEX 1

WP1 - Innovation ecosystems for transformational adaptation in demonstrators					
<i>Title</i>	<i>Main author</i>	<i>Contributor(s)</i>	<i>Year</i>	<i>Journal</i>	<i>Comments on the format and link</i>
Interactive innovation broker: a consensual framework for multi-actor approach practical implementation.	Oscar Bernardez (FEUGA)	J. Domingues, N. Rodriguez-Aubo, W. Filipowska, C. Cotelo	2022	ICERI2022 Proceedings	Scientific article and poster presented at the 15th annual International Conference of Education, Research and Innovation in 2022. Link: 10.21125/iceri.2022.1287
WP2 - Integrated biophysical/socioeconomic framework for modelling multi-sector dynamics					
<i>Title</i>	<i>Main author</i>	<i>Contributor(s)</i>	<i>Year</i>	<i>Journal</i>	<i>Comments on the format and link</i>
Modelling crop water demand under climate change to support water management in agriculture: the case of Sardinia region.	Muhammad Faizan Aslam (CMCC)	Sara Masia, Donatella Spano, Valentina Mereu, Marta Debolini, Richard L. Snyder, Andrea Borgo, Antonio Trabucco	2025	Irrigation Science	Scientific article Link: https://doi.org/10.1007/s00271-025-01027-8
Integrated EU risk assessment framework for modelling multi-sector dynamics	Andrea Rivosecchi (CMCC)	Charalampidis I, Vrontisi Z, Hatterman F, Déandreis C, Trabucco A	2025		Scientific article Not submitted yet
Modelling the influence of atmospheric CO2 on irrigation demand in the vineyard of the Sardinia region	Aslam MF	Borgo A, Masia S, Debolini M, Mereu V, Spano D, Snyder RL, Trabucco A	2025	Bio Web of Conferences	Scientific article Link: to come

High Resolution Global Environmental Stratification to Model Shifting Bioclimatic Conditions and Climate Change Impacts on Terrestrial Ecosystems	Zomer RJ	Metzger M, Xu J, Trabucco A	2025	Open Research Europe	Scientific article Link: to come
WP3 – Envisioning transformative pathways for the demonstrators					
<i>Title</i>	<i>Main author</i>	<i>Contributor(s)</i>	<i>Year</i>	<i>Journal</i>	<i>Comments on the format and link</i>
The road to a sustainable energy system in the Guadeloupe archipelago: Challenges and opportunities	Mostafa Barani (NTNU)	Konstantin Löffler, Luka Garibashvili, Pedro Crespo del Prado	2025	Heliyon	Scientific article. Link: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2025.e41760
Lessons learned on adaptation pathways	Jan Cools/Saioa Zorita	Suzie Durand/Stephane Simonet	2025		Not submitted yet
WP4 - Actionable adaptive solutions implementation					
<i>Title</i>	<i>Main author</i>	<i>Contributor(s)</i>	<i>Year</i>	<i>Journal</i>	<i>Comments on the format and link</i>
Are citizens willing to take action on stormwater management? Adapting to climate change in Finland and Norway	Haoran Yu (UAntwerp)	Amalie Bjornavold, Liuliu Du-Ikonen, Steven Van Passel, Jan Cools	2025	Ecological Economics	Scientific article and presentation to the 30 th Annual Conference of the European Association of Environmental and Resource Economists in 2025. Link: to come
Assessing the Impact of European Initiatives on Mitigating Severe Climate Effects in Egaleo: A Technological and Social Innovation Perspective	Athanasios Sfetsos (NCSRDA)	Vasileios-Alexandros Rafail, Ioannis Zarikos, Stelios Karozis, Athanasios Sfetsos,	2025	Urban Climate Change Research Network Center for Climate Systems Research	Scientific article. Link: https://doi.org/10.7916/c0tr-h031

		and Dimitrios Tzempelikos			
Tropicalization of fish fauna of Galician coastal waters, in the NW Iberian CETMAR Upwelling system. Running page head: Non-native marine fishes in Galicia, Regional	Rafael Bañón (Grupo de Estudio Medio Mariño) (GEMM)	Paula Conde Pardo, Xosé Antón Álvarez-Salgado, Alejandro Carlos, Juan Carlos Arronte and Silvia Piedracoba	2024	Regional Studies in Marine Science	Scientific article. Link: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rsma.2024.103369
CETMAR Seasonal, Interannual and long-term variability of sea Surface temperature in the NW Iberian upwelling - 1982-2020	Silvia Piedracoba (CETMAR)	Paula Conde Pardo, Xosé Antón Álvarez-Salgado, and Silvia Torres	2024	Journal of Geophysical Research: Oceans	Scientific article. Link: https://doi.org/10.1029/2024JC021075
Implementing sedimentary monitoring of Rias Baixas (Galicia) shellfish banks to improve response to changing environmental conditions	Guitian (UVIGO)	Jose Blanco Ramón Casais, Manuela Gómez Pazo, Alejandro Cajade Pascual, Daniel Fontán Bouzas, Ángela González Villanueva, Rita Bernabéu Tello, Ana López Olmedilla, Laura	2022	Cursos e Congresos, XI Jornadas Geomorfología Litoral Galicia 2022	Scientific article presented at XI Conference on Coastal Geomorphology in 2022. Link: https://libros.usc.gal/index.php?id_product=1104&controller=product

Integrated Governance Models for Wetlands and Rivers: The Case of Oristano's Coastal Contract	Manuela Puddu	Francesca Etzi	2025		Not submitted yet
Flood Depth Prediction using Temporal Attention Recurrent Graph Convolutional Neural Network for IoT-Enabled Smart City	Nishu Gupta	Marcos Xosé Alvarez Cid, and Mohammad Derawi,	2025	International Conference on Data Science & Exploration in Artificial Intelligence	Accepted and presented at the 2nd International Conference on Data Science & Exploration in Artificial Intelligence (CODE-AI 2025). Link: to come
IoT and Data-Driven Acoustic Leak Detection Using Microcontroller and Fast Fourier Transform	Mohammad Derawi	Marcos Xosé Alvarez Cid, Faouzi Alaya Cheikh, Neha Gupta, and Nishu Gupta	2025	International Conference on Electrical Engineering, Electronics, Computer Science & Technology	Submitted to the International Conference on Electrical Engineering, Electronics, Computer Science & Technology (IC3ECT 2025), organised by the Research Practice & Publication Forum, Malaysia.
WP5 - Accelerating demonstrators' transformational adaptation					
<i>Title</i>	<i>Main author</i>	<i>Contributor(s)</i>	<i>Year</i>	<i>Journal</i>	<i>Comments on the format and link</i>
Evaluation of the impact of flow pattern and design modifications on the efficiency of wetland treatment via tracer testing		J. a,b,*, M. Šerešc, d, T. Hnátková, A. Sochackia , M. Kaplickád, 4 L. Zídková, J. Vymazala	Published in June 2025	Water and Environment Journal	Article Link: to come
Environmental sustainability of stormwater management practices: insights from a comparative LCA including a nature-based solution in Finland	Ishika Weerawardhan (LUT)	Mariia Zhaurova (LUT), Mari Hupponen (LUT), Mika Horttanainen (LUT)	2025		Scientific article Not submitted yet

Barriers and opportunities for sustainable investors to invest in climate adaptation	Linda Romanovska	Tara Op de Beeck Axelle Vincent Nature4Invest	2025		Article Not submitted yet
Financing nature-based solutions: bridging the gap between public and private financing with debt-financing instruments?	Tara Op de Beeck & Axelle Vincent	Heleen Van Hecke (UA)	2025		Article Not submitted yet
WP6 - Acceptance, building and exploitation of innovation packages (UA)					
<i>Title</i>	<i>Main author</i>	<i>Contributor(s)</i>	<i>Year</i>	<i>Publication type</i>	<i>Comments on the format and link</i>
Citizens' Priorities for Climate Adaptation: A Willingness-to-Pay Approach in Six European Countries Provisional Journal: Climatic Change	Anna Alberini (CMCC)	Andrea Bigano Adan L. Martinez-Cruz	2025	Annual conference of the Italian Climate Sciences Society	Accepted and will be presented at the annual conference of the Italian Climate Sciences Society on October 2 nd -24 th .
Testing for Scope in WTP for Climate Change Adaptation	Anna Alberini (CMCC)	Andrea Bigano Adan L. Martinez-Cruz	2025		Article Not submitted yet
Defining and assessing Transformational Adaptation: the TransformAr Scorecard	Charlotte Fabri	Jan Cools	2025	Environmental Research Communications	Submitted Link: to come

ANNEX 2

TransformAr

Accelerating and upscaling transformational adaptation in
Europe: demonstration of water-related innovation
packages

Communication & Dissemination Strategy

Westcountry Rivers Trust

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon H2020 innovation action programme under grant agreement 101036683.

Deliverable Number and Name	
Work Package	
Dissemination Level	
Author(s)	Emily Widdecombe, Ada Myers, Giles Rickard, Nicola Rogers
Primary Contact and Email	Emilywiddecombe@wrt.org.uk
Date Due	30/04/2025
Date Submitted	
File Name	WRT Communication & Dissemination Strategy
Status	Complete
Reviewed by (if applicable)	N/A
Suggested citation	Author (Year) Deliverable name. TransformAR Deliverable X.X, H2020 grant no. 101036683

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The TransformAr project has produced a variety of valuable outputs suitable for widespread dissemination, both to enhance project impact and to accelerate the uptake of transformational adaptation in Europe. To ensure that outputs are communicated effectively to intended audiences, WRT have produced a communication and dissemination strategy, outlined here. This strategy maps suitable platforms, individual actors and networks within which outputs can be shared or presented during the final six months of the project. WRT staff have collaborated internally to establish high priority communication pathways for each output, and developed an action plan to operationalise this strategy in the coming months.

1.0 TransformAr Project Outputs

2.0 Intended audiences & Actor Mapping

Westcountry Rivers Trust charitable objectives are:

1. To conserve, protect, rehabilitate and improve the rivers, streams, watercourses and water impoundments of the catchments comprising the rivers within the Westcountry, including adjacent estuarine and coastal areas.
2. To advance the education of the public, or any association, company, local authority, administrative or governmental agency or public body or representative body in:
 - a. the understanding of rivers, river corridors and catchments, including their fauna, flora and economic or social activity, and river catchment management
 - b. the need for, and benefits of, conservation, protection, rehabilitation and improvement of aquatic environments.

Communication and dissemination of valuable outputs from the TransformAr project will increase the viability of future nature-based solutions projects in the Westcountry region, and help to embed principles of transformational adaptation at multiple levels across a variety of organisations. The actor mapping matrix below outlines the level of communication required for each intended audience.

These categories can be mapped onto the following communications hierarchy, each tier of which relates to different types of communication platforms and methods:

1.1 Outputs suitable for dissemination

- 1) Bankability Report Methodology & Outcomes for the Southwest Region
- 2) Sustainability Profile of WRT Solutions
- 3) TransformAr Monitoring Report
- 4) Adaptation Planning Methodology
- 5) Policy Brief: Accelerating investment into climate adaptation
- 6) Climate Adaptation Playbook
- 7) Data Visualization Platform
- 8) Mission & Green Deal Success Stories
- 9) Stakeholder Engagement Best Practices
- 10) Policy Briefs x 3
- 11) Replicability Tool & Replication Guide
- 12) Learning Stories

- 13) Discrete Choice Experiment Results
- 14) Transformational Scorecard Methodology & Tool
- 15) WRT Solutions write up

2.0 Dissemination Work Plan

2.1 Suitable Platforms & Dissemination Roadmap

Table 2.1 Dissemination Action Plan

Project Output	Intended Audience(s)	Presentation Opportunities	Platforms	Responsible	Deadline
Bankability Report Methodology & Outcomes for the Southwest Region	Participants in bankability interviews	East Devon and West Dorset Green Finance Group			
	Internally at WRT	Devon Climate Emergency Project	WRT website		
	East Devon and West Dorset Green Finance Group	Southwest Infrastructure Partnership	Social media post with key messages	Emily	July 2025
	Devon Climate Emergency Project	Camel Catchment Partnership			
	Southwest Infrastructure Partnership	CaBa groups – Tamar/Cornwall			
Sustainability Profile of WRT Solutions	Similar practitioners: other Rivers Trusts, FWAG, etc.	WRT Land Team Meeting	WRT Website Social media posts with key messages	Emily	August 2025
TransformAR Monitoring Report	Internally at WRT Rivers Trust Monitoring Working Group	Rivers Trust Monitoring Working Group	WRT website	Ada/Nicola	September 2025
Adaptation Planning & Methodology	Devon Climate Emergency Partnership/Climate Impacts Group	Presentations via other adaptation project groups: RRC, RCC, CROC	Devon Climate Emergency Resources Page	Emily, staff associated with sister projects	July – September 2025
	Local Resilience Forums	CSI Conference	ASSEMBLE		

	Community Groups engaged In CSI				
Policy Brief: Accelerating investment into climate adaptation	DEFRA	ACTION: Collaborate with Jan, Axelle & Tara to develop policy brief on actions needed to accelerate investment into climate adaptation. Review pipeline for policy brief submission.			
Climate Adaptation Playbook	Local Resilience Forum Climate Impacts Group Sister projects: ARSINOE, WaterGrid Community Groups engaged in CSI/RRC	LRF CIG Presentations via other adaptation project groups: RRC, RCC, CROC	DCE Resource Page ASSEMBLE	Emily	May 2025
Data Visualization Platform	ACTION: Review this output to assess use-case. Plan audience & engagement accordingly.				
Mission & Green Deal Success Stories	NOT USEFUL FOR WRT PARTNERS				
Stakeholder Engagement Best Practices Report	Internally at WRT	Land/E.E/Rivers & Fisheries Presentations	WRT website	Emily	May 2025
Replicability Tool & Replication Guide	Rivers Trusts Local Resilience Forums Somerset Levels Project ('Follower' demonstrator) Community Groups engaged in other climate adaptation projects (RRC, RCC, CROC)	CSI Conference	WRT website ASSEMBLE		
Learning Stories	NOT USEFUL FOR WRT PARTNERS				
Discrete Choice Experiment Results & Methodology	To be shared internally at WRT as an available tool/method to apply where relevant in future	1:1 presentations with staff members	WRT website	Emily	June 2025
Transformational Scorecard tool & Methodology	Climate Impacts Group Local Resilience Forum	CIG LRF	DCE Resources Page	Emily	July 2025

	Internally at WRT to inform future project planning: bid team & project teams	Local Authorities	LRF Resources page (?)		
	Community Groups engaged in other climate adaptation projects (RRC, RCC, CROC)	Cornwall Council	WRT Website		
		Catchment Partnerships	Social media		
		Presentations via other adaptation project groups: RRC, RCC, CROC	ASSEMBLE		
		CSI conference			

3.0 Actions

3.1 Workshops

1. Tools for Community Climate Adaptation

Aim: Empower communities with the skills and knowledge necessary to create an adaptation plan for their local area, and to contribute to adaptation projects in future.

1-day workshop promoted to community groups engaged in RRC, RCC, CROC, etc. to present the transformational adaptation scorecards, the replicability tool; climate adaptation playbook, and the methodology for creating an adaptation plan.

Resources:

- WP1 Underspend -> Workshop Budget
- Venue
- Pre- and post-workshop surveys
- Agendas
- Lunch/Refreshment

Climate change impacts are here and now. The impacts on people, prosperity and planet are already pervasive but unevenly distributed, as stated in the new EU Blueprint strategy (European Commission-EC, 2019). To reduce climate-related risks, the EC and the IPCC agree that transformational adaptation is essential. The TransformAr project aims to develop and demonstrate products and services to launch and accelerate large-scale and disruptive adaptive process for transformational adaptation in vulnerable regions and communities across Europe.

The 6 TransformAr lighthouse demonstrators face a common challenge: water-related risks and impacts of climate change. Based on existing successful initiatives, the project will develop, test and demonstrate solutions and pathways, integrated in Innovation Packages, in 6 territories.

Transformational pathways, including an integrated risk assessment approach are co-developed by means of 9 Transformational Adaptive Blocks. A set of 22 tested actionable adaptive solutions are tested and demonstrated, ranging from nature-based solutions, innovative technologies, financing, insurance and governance models, awareness and behavioral change solutions.

TransformAr

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